

'Wisdom of the Crowds' and Online Information Reliability: A Case Study of Israeli Real Estate Websites

Abstract

Purpose – This study aims to determine whether the quality and reliability of websites' content can be assessed through the lens of 'wisdom of the crowds'. In particular, as a case study we examine the information supplied over time on several prominent Israeli real estate websites.

Design/methodology/approach - The Israeli real estate market was selected for our study, since there are many large, popular and dynamic real estate websites that feature hundreds of thousands of ads, representing most of the supply of real estate properties in the country. We built an automatic, ontology-based system that downloaded advertisements from three selected websites every two weeks for a number of months and checked for changes in these advertisements over time. We conjecture that 'wisdom of the crowds' is mostly reflected by the information changes on the websites, since they indicate the anticipated market trends. Hence, we developed a number of statistical measures to comparatively analyze trends of information changes on these websites, and assess their reliability compared to the actual market data and tendencies.

Findings - The primary results suggest similar information change trends amongst all the websites. Surprisingly, though some properties did not sell over time, sellers generally did not lower their asking price and were willing to wait. Sellers even raised their asking price, apparently in anticipation of future price increases. Comparison of recurring trends among the websites to the trends of the real market during the same time-period and a few months after reveals that 'wisdom of the crowds' is only partially effective as an indicator and predictor of website content quality: it correctly reflects the fluctuation in demand, but not in the prices.

Research limitations/implications - This study was conducted over a limited time period of five months, and only in a several cities in Israel. Additionally, since buyers are not explicitly represented in these sites, their information behavior was not analyzed, although it undoubtedly influences information changes performed by the sellers.

Practical contribution - The practical contribution of this study is the ontology of the real estate world. Its assimilation by online real estate websites would promote the development of their sites and user services. It would also enable ad sharing amongst the various websites and enable efficient searches by search engines. In addition, the tools and measures that we developed will allow continued monitoring and analyzing user information change patterns.

Originality/value - To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to examine and compare online real estate websites quality and evaluate their information reliability as 'wisdom of the crowds'.

1. Introduction

The internet provides a global information infrastructure that enables the creation of websites and applications for the purchase of goods and services overcoming technical problems such as geographic and time differences. Many e-commerce sites have become extremely popular (Amazon, eBay), and today e-commerce is a central component of most companies' business activities.

Real estate is a market area that has successfully transferred to the virtual world. Today, many countries have dozens of general real estate websites. In addition, there are local classified websites, managed by private real estate agencies and sites that specialize in specific types of properties, such as luxury apartments. In Israel, there are close to 100,000 advertisements on the most popular classified

sites, such as yad2.co.il, at any given time. We can conclude that the online second-hand real estate market is a popular model, changing dynamically and sufficiently large in scope (in relation to the real market supply).

As opposed to most online transactions, many real estate deals do not involve business entities. Generally, the transactions on these real estate websites are conducted between private users (buyer and seller), though companies (such as, real estate agencies and construction companies) also present their listings on these websites. The website services are generally free of charge and allow advertisement of real estate properties for sale. In addition, the service includes an interface that facilitates sophisticated searches. Hence, real estate websites' content is assumed to reflect the 'wisdom of the crowds' viewpoint on the actual situation and trends of the actual market. Consequently, users search the ads on these websites not just to buy or rent properties, but also to receive market updates and analyze the actual real estate market conditions. Therefore, the quality and the reliability of the content on the real estate websites becomes quite crucial issue.

Numerous frameworks and measures for online information quality evaluation were presented in the past two decades (Eppler and Wittig, 2000; Klein, 2002; Knight and Burn, 2005). The most prominent criteria from the literature are accuracy, completeness, authority (known and visible author), relevance, maintainability, accessibility, timeliness (being up-to-date), and usability. However, most of the measures are not applicable to the user generated content. Hence, in the later review (Chai et al., 2009) the authors highlight social content quality measures which are better fitted to assessment of content quality in the social web environment, e.g. internet forums, blogs, and social recommendation sites. The latter measure list includes user feedback, amount of data, reputation, objectivity, believability, consistency, value-added and security. Yet, quality evaluation of user generated commercial content like property advertisements on real estate websites were not addressed in these studies.

Hence, the goal of this work is to determine the credibility of the information uploaded by thousands of users for other users on the e-commerce websites. To this end, we explore the possibility to regard the information content of these sites as 'wisdom of the crowds'. This content quality can be then evaluated by the reliability of the trends dictated by the collective intelligence on these sites during a period when market experts had divided opinions about anticipated trends. We argue that in the dynamic online environments, trends are represented by continuing repetitive patterns of information changes over time. Hence, to reveal these trends we explored the information and the change patterns in information implemented by private sellers in the online marketplace, focusing on the Israeli real estate websites as a case study. In particular, we surveyed the actions, over time, that advertisers implemented to promote the sale of their property, in order to identify permanent information change patterns. Further, several quantitative measures were defined to analyze these changes and assess the quality of the corresponding websites. A first aspect of the study was a comparison of the various websites and an identification of the differences between them based on the suggested measures. In addition, we analyzed whether the website information was influenced by the concurrent changes on the real market, and what was their impact on the real market.

For the above purposes, we developed an information system based on real estate ontology. The data in the system was downloaded from the largest real estate sites in Israel: Yad2, Winwin, and Homeless. The system traced the advertised data on these sites and aggregated modifications that were made over time, such as changes to prices in various geographic areas and different types of properties. The system was activated for five consecutive months in 2012, during which we monitored changes to the website data. Simultaneously, we followed media reports about real estate market conditions as a factor that could possibly influence the website changes.

2. Literature Review

2.1. E-commerce and the Online Real Estate Market

"E-commerce is the purchase and sale of information, products and services through computer networks" (Kalakota and Whinston, 1997). *E-commerce can be divided into Five Primary Categories (Schneider, 2010):*

1. B2C – Business to Consumer. A transaction that takes place between a business entity and a private consumer (generally domestic). For this purpose, the business entity develops a website that serves as a virtual store.
2. B2B – Business to Business. Transactions that take place between two business entities, through private infrastructure or through infrastructure provided by a third party.
3. Business Processes. Business processes that service and support sale and purchase activities. Organizations and companies share information to identify and evaluate customers, suppliers and employees.
4. C2C – Consumer to Consumer. Transactions that takes place between two private consumers (e.g. EBay, the public auction website).
5. B2G – Business to Government. Transactions that takes place between a business entity and a government entity.

This study focuses on the consumer to consumer (C2C) model and presents facts related to second hand real estate. It does not relate to agencies or construction companies, in order to neutralize the influence of large companies and cartels on market trends. These firms generally sell new properties and are influenced by political and economic factors that are peripheral to the decisions of private individuals.

Previous research indicates that as it developed, the internet has become an efficient source for gathering information (Jud, Winkler and Sirmans, 2002) that allows for efficient acquisition of information at low costs (Benjamin, Jud and Sirmans, 2000). Specifically in the realm of real estate, home buyers and sellers generally use the internet in their search (Crowston and Wigand, 1999; Bond et al., 2000; Benjamin et al., 2005).

Many sites on the internet provide information regarding mortgages, characteristics of neighborhoods and areas, and interesting points about various districts (Seiler, Seiler and Webb, 2006). A new study from the United States (Beracha and Wintoki, 2013) found that an increase in the amount of Google searches for real estate properties in a specific area could predict short-term changes in the prices of properties in that area (in the following quarter, and even in the next eight quarters). The researchers also found that a decrease in property visits caused sellers to refuse to lower their prices.

Seiler, Madhavan and Liechty (2012) used ocular tracking technology to study behavior patterns of people looking to purchase a home. Their study found that the homebuyers first focused on the picture of the homes and then on the verbal description. Only 60% looked at the verbal comments. Thus, undoubtedly adding images or a video of the offered property is one of the most effective selling strategies. In contrast, in this paper we specifically investigate strategic advertising patterns and information changes expressed in the textual form.

2.2. Wisdom of the crowds

Surowiecki (2005) claims that a crowd's "collective intelligence" will produce better outcomes than a small group of experts, even if members of the crowd don't know all the facts or choose, individually,

to act irrationally, if four basic conditions are met: (1) diversity of opinion; (2) independence of members from one another; (3) decentralization; and (4) a good method for aggregating opinions.

Further research (Giles, 2005) shows that wisdom of the crowds is successfully used as a tool in many areas, such as, for sorting information and correcting mistakes on Wikipedia (Wikipedia.com), predicting future market trends (Surowiecki, 2005), improving stock markets trends prediction via Google trends (Pierse et al., 2008) and enhancing flu outbreaks prediction by twitter messages (Harshavardhan et al., 2012). An interesting recent study by (Bollen and Mao, 2011) indicates that people's moods on Twitter can quite accurately predict future short-term stock market trends. On Web2.0, collective intelligence is reflected in various realms, such as product opinions (IMDb.com, Amazon.com), Wikipedia content creation (Kittur, 2008), information tagging (flicker.com), and social bookmarking (delicious.com). It has successfully been used for semantic tagging (Wu et al., 2006; Bar-Ilan et al., 2010), constructing folksonomies (Trant, 2009) and even in citizen science (Hand, 2010).

As mentioned in the previous section, multiple measures for assessment of the World Wide Web information were proposed in the past research (e.g. Eppler and Wittig, 2000; Klein, 2002; Knight and Burn, 2005; Chai et al., 2009). These measures include accuracy, completeness, authority, relevance, maintainability, accessibility, timeliness, and usability, user feedback, amount of data, reputation, objectivity, believability, consistency, security and more. However, it is unclear how to apply these measures to information content which is dynamically generated and updated by a bunch of unknown users. This situation calls for developing new measures for this type of websites as 'wisdom of the crowds'. Therefore, one of the goals of this study is to determine whether wisdom of the crowds applies to users of the online marketplace of C2C model. In particular, does the information created dynamically by 'wisdom of the crowds' on the real estate websites enable the reliable reflection and prediction of active and future trends?

3. The System for Information Aggregation Based on the Ontology of the Real Estate World

Currently, to advertise an apartment for sale on the internet and receive maximum exposure, its owners must approach the different websites and fill out different details about the apartment on each site. Likewise, buyers looking for an apartment must conduct searches according to their criteria on the different sites. They waste valuable time and effort while moving from site to site and synchronizes their information to the different informational schemas designated by each site. The primary difficulty is that the various sites do not 'speak' the same 'language'. This complicates things for automated 'intelligent' real estate agents which can only transfer information from sites whose 'language' they recognize. This generates the need for a generic, uniform schema for real estate ads, which will serve as a unified language to inclusively and unequivocally describe the myriads of details and facts in this vital domain of knowledge.

Hence, a joint vocabulary, i.e. an ontology, must be implemented in order to standardize the information from the various websites.

3.1 The Ontological Model for the Real Estate World

“An ontology is a formal explicit description of concepts in a domain of discourse (classes [...]), properties of each concept [...] (slots [...]), and restrictions on slots (facets [...])” (Noy and McGuinness, 2001). Though an ontology can be represented in various formats, it will always include vocabulary that is built of terms and their significant relationships (Jasper and Uschold, 1999). The utilization of ontology enables (Noy and McGuinness, 2001) sharing of common understanding of the structure of information among people or software agents and reuse of domain knowledge.

Since, to the best of our knowledge, there is no previous ontology for the world of real estate, we suggest the broadening of the ontology model of schema.org. Schema.org (<http://www.schema.org>) is the common Semantic Web initiative of the three giant search engines: Google, Yahoo! and Microsoft Bing. The goal of this initiative is the development of a detailed ontological hierarchy of classes in various domains. This hierarchy can be broadened for specific realms of knowledge by the users. In addition, the initiative provides simple tools for integrating this semantic information within the users' HTML pages. The benefits of this technology are that it allows the large search engines, which initiated this project, to use this information to promote the sites; and it enables the encoding of the information with relative technological ease, in contrast to the classic ontology languages (such as RDF and OWL) which are more complicated for inexpert users. The use of these schemas will allow the search engines to better 'understand' the information on the site. The search engines will then present the information in a uniform format and will provide more accurate and exhaustive search results. Consequently, users will not need to search each and every real estate site separately.

As a first step, we analyzed the information details that exist on the selected classified websites. In Israel there is a number of large websites with listings of ads for sale and rental of real estate properties. The most prominent ones are:

1. Yad2 (<http://www.yad2.co.il/Nadlan/sales.php>)
2. Winwin (<http://www.winwin.co.il/RealEstate/ForSale/RealEstatePage.aspx>)
3. Homeless (<http://www.homeless.co.il>)

To generalize, we also analyzed a number of foreign sites, such as, Yandex.ru, Homes.com and Zillow.com.

For instance, the sites designated the type of property, its geographic location in the country, its size and condition and its price. Some sites, like Yad2, provide auxiliary information from government and other sources, such as information regarding transactions made in the area of the selected property, pictures of the street on which the property is located, a map marked with additional properties in the region, and even information regarding neighbors and educational institutions in the area.

The second step was to decide which of the existing classes in schema.org were the most suitable for extension and integration in the ontology for the Real Estate domain.

After a comprehensive review of the existing hierarchy, a number of classes were found that can be integrated into the suggested ontology:

Thing, the root class of the hierarchy of schema.org, all other classes descend from it; *PostalAddress*; *Person*; *Place* which describes a geographic location; *RealEstateAgent*.

In addition, two new classes were designated:

1. *RealEstateProperty*: describes the real estate property
2. *RealEstateOffer*: identifies an ad for sale of real estate property

It was necessary to create new classes despite the fact that the schema in schema.org includes a *Product* and an *Offer* classes, since they describe a sale offer of a consumer product and were, as such, irrelevant to the characteristics of real estate properties.

A UML schema presented in Figure 1 describes the various classes and the relationships between them.

Figure 1. UML schema of ontology classes.

3.2 Building an Information Aggregation System

After developing the ontological model, we designed a system to monitor the ads on the various sites over time for comparative purposes. The basis of the system is the ontology that serves as a uniform language which translates all ad particulars on the various websites and enables the analysis of the collected data. The system allows for comparison between the websites in terms of scope and quantity of information. It also answers fundamental questions regarding the quality of this information, such as, comparison of the online change trends in price levels and demands in specific areas over time to the actual market data.

The role of the aggregation module was to serve as an intelligent agent that could access each site, request pages with desired information, transform it to ontology and then transfer it to the processing module. This process is demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: General description of the system's information flow.

Each new ad on all websites was automatically given a unique identification number through which our system could re-identify it during future reviews. When the processing module identified information regarding a specific property on the same website that already existed in the system (in other words, if an ad with this identification number already exists), it was compared to the facts in the database. The results of these comparisons were stored in the database as well and the original records were continuously updated.

4. Research Methodology: Comparative Measures to Identify and Assess Trends in the Online Real Estate Market

The above system monitored three Israeli classified websites (Yad2, Winwin, Homeless), with a focus on properties in ten cities throughout the country: Ashdod, Ashkelon, Be'er Sheva, Haifa, Jerusalem, Netanya, Petah Tikva, Kiryat Shemona, Rishon L'Tzion and Tel Aviv. These cities were chosen as the largest cities in their regions. The program scanned each website once every two weeks, on the tenth and thirtieth day of each month.

After activating the system and collecting information for over five months (the second and third quarters of 2012), we conducted a comparative statistical analyses to evaluate the quality of each classified website. To this end, the following measures for assessing information trends were devised:

1. The scope and quantity of information on each website (enabling to estimate the website's popularity).
2. The number of changes to the website data over the duration of the study (the amount of ads that were added or removed over the test period might capture the site's timeliness and the trends of apartment demand).
3. Accompanying informational services (reflecting the site's informativity).
4. Number of modifications to the classified ads (changes made by property owners to their ads on the real estate website over time as an indication of market trends as perceived by 'wisdom of the crowds').
5. Changes to the price of properties over time (this is another indication of market trends through the glasses of 'wisdom of the crowds').
6. The influence of location on the quantity of modifications and type of price modification (helps specify the trend's areas).

Likewise, we compared the changes made to the parameters according to our system to the real market trends (changes in price and demand levels) during the corresponding time period and reviewed real trends during the quarter before and quarter after our system's review. These real market figures were recently published by the Ministry of Construction and Housing (http://www.moch.gov.il/meyda_statisti/mechirey_diyur/Pages/mechirim_memutsaim_shel_dirot.aspx).

We assume that an increase or decrease over time in the amount of changes to a website or its ads indicates growth or stagnation, respectively, in real market activity. Measures two and four allow to identify these trends, and measures five and six allow to identify anticipated changes to real estate prices according to the websites that we analyzed.

In addition, to reach a conclusion regarding the application of 'wisdom of the crowds' or collective intelligence in the online market, we analyzed the characteristics of the sellers who used the online real estate classified websites in relation to the Surowiecki's (2005) criteria of 'wisdom of the crowds'. Each person should have private information even if it's just an eccentric interpretation of the known facts. The diversity brings in different information, as the best decisions are result of disagreement and contest. Independence keeps people from being swayed by a single opinion leader. People's opinions are not determined by the opinions of those around them. People are able to specialize and draw on local knowledge. People's errors balance each other out. Finally, some mechanism exists for turning private judgments into a collective decision, while including all opinions guarantees that the results are 'smarter' than if a single expert had been in charge" (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Wisdom_of_Crowds/).

To analyze the criteria number three (decentralization), we monitored the influence of reports in the media on information change types to ads and in particular, modifications of property prices. Note that this study does not compare cross-website ad duplicates due to the difficulties in identifying where the same (partial) addresses are appearing multiple times.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Scope and Quantity of Information on each Website

Information was collected from May 5, 2012 through September 30, 2012. To compare the amount of information on each real estate website, we noted the number of general ads (throughout the country) on each site at the start and in the end of the review period. This information is featured in Table 1.

Table 1: Quantity of ads throughout the country.

Website	Number of Ads on 05/10	Number of Ads on 09/30	Rate of Increase in %
Yad2	81,220	84,548	4.10
Winwin	52,167	55,497	6.38
Homeless	3,396	3,466	2.06
Total	136,783	143,511	4.91

On average, there was about 5% increase in the number of general ads on the three websites. Surprisingly, Winwin had the highest rate of increase, almost 1.5 times more than Yad2, the biggest classified website. This increase is possibly related to the aggressive marketing and advertising campaign conducted during this period by Winwin. In addition, the general growth reflects directly the increase of market supply, and could indirectly indicate resurgence in the real estate market which was slow prior to our review period (in 2011).

5.2 Number of Changes to the Websites Over Time (in the Ten Cities Included in the Review)

Figure 3 represents the quantity of ads on each site that were added, removed or remained of the total amount of ads reviewed on the website (in percentages) during the entire period of time.

Figure 3. Percentages of ads that were added, removed or remained on each website.

The data indicates that most of the ads on the large websites, Yad2 and Winwin, were posted for more than five months. On all sites, the amount of ads that were added is higher than the amount of ads that were removed. Based on the conjecture that ads were removed after the properties were sold (in most cases), we can infer that less than one-third of the properties were successfully sold in less than five months. Parallel to the data from the previous clause, this information reflects an increase in supply, and, indirectly, a rise in market activity. From the total of all ads reviewed, 25% of ads on Yad2 and Winwin, and over 35% on Homeless, were added after the first survey. Homeless featured a larger amount of ads that were added than remained throughout the entire period, testifying to a higher level of turnover and being up-to-date. Again following the assumption that ads were removed after the properties were sold, Homeless is the most effective of the three classified real estate websites. However, we note that this is the only website that charges a fee for posting ads, a factor which could also influence the turnover rate of the ads.

5.3 Auxiliary Services

Table 2 details the auxiliary services provided by each website.

Table 2: Comparison of websites' auxiliary services.

Type of service	Yad2	Winwin	Homeless
Map of Area	Y	Y	Y
Picture of Street	Y	Y	
Apartment Pricelist	Y	Y	
Data Regarding Area Residents	Y		
Interesting Points About Area	Y		Y
Property Prices in Area (from the same website)	Y		

This table indicates that Yad2 provides the most auxiliary services (six), two of which are unique to this website. It is followed by Winwin, with three services, and Homeless comes in last with only two services.

5.4 Number of Modification to Website Ads

Table 3 presents the number of ads on each website that were modified during the entire period.

Table 3: Number of ads that were changed.

Website	Number of Ads that were Changed	Percentage of Total Ads
Yad2	5,078	11.20
Winwin	3,146	14.62
Homeless	116	5.77
Total	8,340	12.12

Analysis of the number of ads that were modified by the sellers indicates that most ads remained unchanged for a long time. Only one out of every ten ads was modified during the review period, about five months, on both of the big websites (Yad2 and Winwin). The figures were even lower on the smaller site, Homeless, where only one out of every twenty ads were modified. Figure 4 represents the types of changes that were made.

Figure 4. Types of changes and their percentages.

Figure 4 indicates that price changes were substantially more common than any other change. The second most common change was to the comment section (a seller's textual description of the offered property). Table 4 demonstrates the percentage of each type of change for each website.

Table 4: Percentage of each type of change on each Website.

Website	Price Changes	Changes to the Comment Section	Other Changes
Yad2	72.19	14.49	13.32
Winwin	69.87	18.34	11.79
Homeless	65.96	25.38	8.66

Table 4 indicates that price changes were the most overwhelmingly common modification on each website. The table also clearly shows that significantly less 'other' changes were made to Homeless than to the other websites. This is apparently related to the fee that this website charges, which promotes precise descriptions from the outset, eliminating the need for future changes.

Figure 5: Relationship between the review date of the ad and the quantity of changes.

Figure 5 displays the graph of continuous changes in ads over time. With this data, one can discern that besides for a slow, moderate rise in the number of changes over time, there is a jump in the amount of changes during the months of July-August, which should indicate an accelerating market and an increase in market demand during this period. This trend stops at the end of September, which is also when the system's review period concluded.

5.5 Price Modifications

Table 5 exhibits the amount of advertisements in which the asking price was lowered or increased during the review period, of the total amount of ads with price modifications.

Table 5: Type of change and its percentage of the total price modifications on each site.

Website	Decrease	Increase
Yad2	33.76	66.24
Winwin	31.47	68.53
Homeless	44.08	55.92
Average of all ads	33.17	66.83

This table marks almost identical data from the larger websites, Yad2 and Winwin: only one-third of the sellers lowered their asking price during the test period. This is surprising in face of the fact that most of the ads remained on the website for about a half a year. Even though the properties were not sold, the sellers raised their prices instead of the intuitive solution of decreasing the asking price to promote quick sales. This information change pattern, which repeated itself on all the websites, indicates that the sellers anticipated a rise in prices and an acceleration in the market. There are a number of explanations for this phenomenon, such as the fact that most of the sellers are not pressured to sell their property in a short period of time and anticipate the one buyer willing to give them their high asking price (investors and housing 'upsizers'). In addition, housing 'upsizers' looking to purchase nicer and new apartments, faced rising prices on new apartments during this period, so they needed to raise the asking price on the properties that they were selling. The quantity of price increases and decreases was more balanced on the Homeless website. It is possible to extrapolate that this is due to the fee that Homeless charges, which encourages sellers to post attractive (lower) prices upfront in order to sell their property as fast as possible.

Figure 6 represents the average price of real estate according to all the websites during the review period. It indicates a persistent, steady increase that intensified at the start of the third quarter and faded at its end.

Figure 6: Average price in the ads at the beginning and end of the review period.

5.6 Influence of Area on Price Modifications

Table 6 represents the percentage of change to the average price and the percentage of modifications to the ads in each city (on the three websites).

Table 6. Percentage of change to the average price and the percentage of changes to the total ads in each city.

City	Changes to Ads	Change to Average Price
Ashdod	9.43	5.53
Ashkelon	10.27	2.41
Be'er Sheva	11.82	3.62
Haifa	12.64	4.58
Jerusalem	12.29	3.73
Netanya	11.95	3.61
Petah Tikva	12.73	4.38
Kiryat Shemona	6.69	1.27
Rishon L'Tzion	11.34	4.49
Tel Aviv	12.68	4.13

One can roughly see that about one out of ten ads were modified in all of the cities. The least amount of modifications was made in Kiryat Shemona, apparently indicating the slow market in the north of the country. The change to the average price ranged around 4%. Surprisingly, Ashdod, which is

located in the south (and not in the center), had the highest rate of change to its average price, with a 5.53% change. This might indicate that this city saw the sharpest rise in demand.

5.7 Comparison between the Information Change Trends on the Real Estate Websites and the Official Data regarding Actual Transactions during the Same Period

In short, the results of the measures reviewed above (1, 2, 4, and 5) indicate that the trends of increased demand reflected on the online real estate websites (as presented in Table 1, and Figures 3, 7 and 5) match the official statistics of the Ministry of Housing and Construction (http://www.moch.gov.il/meyda_statisti/habikush_beshuk_hadiyur/Pages/habikush_beshuk_hadiyur.aspx). According to their reports, there was a persistent increase in the amount of transactions from quarter to quarter at a yearly rate of 24%. In other words, the market did resurge after a slowdown and had an accelerated level of activity. The sharpest increase took place between the second and third quarter as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Number of transactions in second-hand apartments in Israel during 2012, according to calendar quarters.

Figure 8: Comparison between the fluctuations in average price in the online market in contrast to the real market, according to regions in the country. The official data was taken from: http://www.moch.gov.il/meyda_statisti/mechirey_diyur/Pages/mechirim_memutsaim_shel_dirof.aspx#GovXParagraphTitle2.

Figure 8 compares the percentage of change to the average price of second hand apartments in 2012 according to the official data of the Ministry of Construction and Housing to the changes in average price in the same regions and during the same period on the real estate websites.

As can be observed from Figure 8, the prediction for price increase on the websites was only partially accurate. According to the websites, there was a price rise between the second and third quarter, and consistently throughout the third quarter. In contrast, according to the official data, the price levels decreased in Tel Aviv, Haifa and in the center of the country over this period. The prices increased only in Jerusalem and on the periphery (north and south), where the websites predicted more modest changes.

Figure 6, including data from the real estate websites, indicates that the average price of the apartments marked a stable increase over the entire period of review (May-September), which became stronger in the middle of the third quarter and more moderate at the end (September). This supports the resurgent market anticipated in Figure 5. In actuality, the average price in the second quarter increased by a paltry 0.04% to reach the average price in the third quarter, in all areas. This contrasts with the over 3% average increase indicated on the websites. In other words, the real market marked stable average prices throughout the country in the second and third quarters with mixed trends, a rise in some areas and decrease in others. These trends continued in the last quarter of 2012. Hence, the website's prediction for price changes was neither fulfilled during the trial period itself, nor in the close following period. However, substantial price increases in all regions of the country were seen during the first quarter, the period before our review. Perhaps this price increase influenced the mood of the sellers who anticipated the continuation of this trend throughout the year.

It is shown in the literature that rise in demand causes property owners to anticipate a parallel rise in prices (Beracha and Wintoki, 2013). However, this natural expectation which is clearly expressed on the three websites that were analyzed, were only fulfilled in certain areas. In fact, the average price on the websites increased steadily throughout the entire period, with less changes to the properties located on the periphery of the country. These areas also marked lower price increase than properties located in the center of the country. In actuality, it was specifically the cities in the periphery that saw

relatively, significant price increases in contrast to the center of the country where real market prices decreased.

The following table represents the average price (at the end of the period) on each website.

Table 7: The average price on ads on each website.

Website	Average Price (In Shekels)
Yad2	1,631,438
Winwin	1,626,673
Homeless	1,541,290

All sites had similar average prices, though Homeless had the lowest average price. This correlates with the data on Table 6, and can strengthen the assertion that the fee charged by Homeless influences its advertisers to publicize more attractive (lower) prices so that their properties sell as soon as possible. Interestingly, the average price on the websites is about 40-50% higher than the actual average price (1,100,000 NIS according to http://www.moch.gov.il/meyda_statisti/mechirey_diyur/Pages/mechirim_memutsaim_shel_dirod.aspx#GovXParagraphTitle2), and is closer to the price of new apartments.

In summary, the information change trends and the price levels presented on the real estate websites examined in this study were revealed as untrustworthy related to the price changes in the real market. However, trends related to the level of market demand are reliably reflected by the information on these sites.

5.8 Analysis of the Sellers on the Online Real Estate Market according to the Criteria of Wisdom of the crowds

There is no doubt that every property seller on the different real estate websites has her own opinion regarding future trends in the real estate market. However, is there a mutual influence between the sellers on the real estate markets? There is no direct communication or discussion between members of this group, and, therefore, no 'groupthink' (Esser, 1998).

In order to evaluate the presence of centralization which could have influenced the sellers on the real estate websites, media publications during the review period must be scanned. The background for this media survey was the 2011 governmental decisions and steps to decrease prices in the wake of the housing shortage, the sharp increase of prices, in tens of percentage points, in the few previous years and the Israeli social justice protests in the summer of 2011 (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2011_Israeli_social_justice_protests). These factors triggered the market freeze in 2011 and a feeling of confusion and lack of certainty throughout 2012.

The following articles were published at the beginning of 2012 through the third quarter. We analyzed the important economic news websites: Ynet's Calcalist, TheMarker, Globes, and Forbes.

Table 8: Summary of the controversial news websites reports on the real estate market.

Articles anticipating a rise in prices and demand	Articles predicting decreases and stability in housing prices
"The Frozen Market Has Defrosted: 36% Decrease in the Scope of Mortgages in May". (Published on 11/06/2012 on TheMarker : (http://www.themarker.com/markets/1.1728849) [Hebrew].	"The Banks Predict: Housing Prices Dropped – Mortgage Conditions to Become More Difficult". (Published on 10/04/2012 on TheMarker: http://www.themarker.com/realestate/1.1683094 .) [Hebrew].
"Social Protests? Housing Prices Rose 0.7% in	"The Treasury: The Price of New Apartments

May. (Published on 15/07/2012 on Globes: http://www.globes.co.il/news/article.aspx?did=1000765941) [Hebrew].	Declined 3% in the First Quarter of 2012". (Published on 16/05/2012 on Calcalist: www.calcalist.co.il/real_estate/articles/0,7340,L-3571355,00.html .) [Hebrew].
The peak arrived in August, apparently due to the VAT increase implemented in September. "Buying an apartment? The VAT Increase will Shave Your Salary". (Published on 29/07/2012 on Globes: http://www.globes.co.il/news/article.aspx?did=1000769610 .) [Hebrew].	Deloitte's Real Estate Review: Housing Prices are Anticipated to Drop 20% this Year". (Published on 22/05/2012 on Forbes: http://www.forbes.co.il/news/new.aspx?Pn6VQ=&0r9VQ=FHF .) [Hebrew].
"The Government Appraiser Published Data Revealing that for the First Time This Year the Listed Apartments for Sale have Become Significantly More Expensive". (Published on 13.8.12 on Calcalist: http://www.calcalist.co.il/real_estate/articles/0,7340,L-3579883,00.html .) [Hebrew].	"Bank of Israel: Stable Housing Prices Lower the Need for New Measures". (Published on 11/06/2012 on Calcalist: http://www.calcalist.co.il/local/articles/0,7340,L-3573732,00.html .) [Hebrew].
"Sharp, 18% Decline in Demand for Mortgages in August". (Published on 20/09/2012 on YNET: http://www.ynet.co.il/articles/0,7340,L-4284153,00.html .) [Hebrew].	"Prices and Amount of Transactions on the Real Estate Market Have Stabilized. (Published on 04/07/2012 on TheMarker: http://www.themarker.com/realestate/yad2/1.1747594 .) [Hebrew].
"Bank of Israel: Worried About the Increase in Housing Prices – But no Intervention". (Published on 09/10/2012 on Globes: http://www.globes.co.il/news/article.aspx?did=100078846 .) [Hebrew]	"Night Frank's Survey 2012: "Israel is Ranked thirty first in the rise in price during the last year, as pricing hasn't changed". (Published on 09/09/2012 on TheMarker: http://www.themarker.com/realestate/1.1820313 .) [Hebrew].

As can be observed, the media announcements and articles from different official sources are diversified and contradictory. Therefore, we can determine that 'centralization' was not present in our case, and there was no dominant, widely-publicized opinion that could have dictated market participants' expectations and behavior.

The fourth criterion (existing of the data aggregation method) is present in our system which collects and analyzes the changes to the ads and evaluates the directions and trends of these changes based on collective intelligence. In conclusion, it seems that the behavior of the group virtually fulfills the principle of wisdom of the crowds.

6. Conclusion

In the framework of this study, the quality of textual information on the online Israeli real estate websites as a product of the 'wisdom of the crowds' was examined and compared. The research followed the dynamic changes in this information over a period of almost two quarters in 2012, when there was a lack of certainty and differences of opinions amongst the official sources, experts and media regarding future market trends. To gather and analyze the ads' information on the online real

estate sites, an automated system based on a new real estate ontology was built as an extension to schema.org ontology. This ontology if adopted by other websites have can create a common language and increase interoperability for sophisticated automatic agents providing real estate services. It could also significantly simplify the process and save user time for searching and advertising of real estate properties as accepted schema.org extensions are used in site's indexing by three biggest search engines (Google, Bing and Yahoo!). In addition, comparative measures were developed to identify and evaluate the information quality and reliability as 'wisdom of the crowds' in the online real estate market. These measures were mostly based on the amount of information and amount and types of modifications to the information on these sites.

Overall, the information presented on the real estate websites was found as quite unreliable compared to the realistic trends of the market during the test period itself, such as price levels and price change trends. They were also only partially successful in predicting, future short-term trends. However, the steady, significant rise in the demand for apartments was well reflected in the online market.

A comprehensive analysis of the results indicates that there were similar information change patterns on the three monitored central real estate websites in the country. For example, only one in every ten ads was changed at all on both of the large websites (and even less on the smaller one). Most of the changes (70%) were made to the price of the property. In addition, most of the ads remained on the sites throughout the review period (other than Homeless, which charges a fee for ads ranging between 69 and about 130 NIS a month, where only 37% of the ads remained during the entire length of the period). Surprisingly, though we would have expected sellers to decrease their asking price if their property was not sold, that is not what happened. Our findings indicate that while most of the ads remained for an extended period (over five months), the sellers on all the websites actually increased their asking price in about two-thirds of these cases. It is possible though that continuing the experiment for a longer period of time could influence the results.

The above conclusion also calls in question the ability of these websites to serve as a tool for surveying the market for users interested in clarifying reasonable market prices for properties. It can be assumed that the buyers' opinion and behavior, which is not directly expressed on the online websites, is what critically influences the real market trends.

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